

Supplementary material

Additional discussion is provided for Section 4.1 to explore the threshold for generating two distinct networks.

Vehicular Network Results Discussion

The best and worst results from the random sample set for each objective are shown for the vehicular network in Fig. 11. Number indices with 1 and 2 are the highest-rated solutions, while 3 and 4 are the lowest-rated.

Vehicular Network

Figure 11. Visualization of selected results from the model random sampling. It shows the two best and two worst solutions for each vehicle network objective in each row. Smaller values (left) indicate better performance.

Solutions with the lowest vehicular network length (g1-g2) predominantly use cul-de-sacs. In these solutions, access to parcels is provided primarily from the road at the site periphery. In contrast, the solutions like h2 with the best vehicular reach have fully connected networks more often with roads that cut directly across the site along one or both primary axes (North-South / East-West). Consistent with the observed negative correlation between these objectives, solution g2 (best in V-Length) is identical to h4 (worst in V_Reach). The results with the lowest number of cul-de-sacs (j1, j2) are very similar to those with highest V_Reach (i.e., h2). The results

with the highest number of cul-de-sacs (j3, j4) do not present optimal V_Length values: while a small number of cul-de-sacs are effective in reducing the length of the vehicular network, additional cul-de-sacs do not offer further benefit.

The visualized results with high straightness values for the vehicular network (i1, i2) have a high number of roads cutting directly across the short axis of the site (North / South) and present high regularity of block distribution. Thus, i1 and i2 share some visual similarity with k1 and k2 (V_Areavariance) an expected resulting given the moderate positive correlation measured between these two objectives. Results with the poor V_Straightness (i3, i4) are distinguished by notably asymmetrical road distribution, have lower V_Length, and include cul-de-sacs.

Similarities found between vehicular network and pedestrian network

Though the pedestrian and vehicular network solutions share similarities due to the modeling algorithm (Section 3.1). The solutions with the lowest pedestrian network length (a1, a2) are similar to the results with the shortest V_Length (g1, g2). Solutions g1 and a2 are identical. This is an expected result given the positive correlation (0.73) between V_Length and P_Length. Solutions with the lowest number of crosswalks and junctions (d1, d2, e1, e2) are similar to the solutions with the lowest V_Length. Solution d1 presents the same vehicular network as g1 and the identical pedestrian network to a2.